

Modeling of a packed bed membrane reactor for ammonia synthesis: on the role of membrane performance and operating conditions

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ABSTRACT

Ammonia (NH₃) has gained attention as a potential hydrogen carrier for its high hydrogen content and absence of carbon atoms. However, the main route for ammonia production is still the energy intensive Haber-Bosch process. In this study, the membrane reactor technology is proposed as an alternative to integrate ammonia synthesis reaction and its simultaneous separation within a single unit. A non-isothermal 1-D packed bed membrane reactor model was developed, in which ammonia synthesis is promoted by a ruthenium-based catalyst, and its in situ separation takes place by means of NH₃-selective membranes. The mathematical model was first validated with experimental data in a packed bed reactor, and afterward used to study the feasibility of a packed bed membrane reactor, aiming to identify the optimal membrane performance required to enhance the reactor efficiency, in terms of H₂ conversion, NH₃ purity and NH₃ recovery. Initial results under isothermal conditions, demonstrate that a $\mathcal{P}_{\text{NH}_3} > 10^{-7} \text{ mol Pa}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $S_{\text{NH}_3/\text{H}_2} = 50$ are required to significantly boost H₂ conversion. On the other hand a $S_{\text{NH}_3/\text{N}_2} = 100$ was selected as a trade-off value influencing NH₃ purity and NH₃ recovery. The operating conditions study revealed that both sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio and pressure difference across the membrane are crucial for enhancing reactor performance, with optimal conditions identified at SW = 6 and ΔP = 20 bar. Furthermore, in the adiabatic case study, the investigation of the heat exchange integration between feed gas and sweep gas streams, highlights the importance of the latter as cooling fluid, achieving the best results at inlet permeate temperature of 200 °C. This enabled to achieve an H₂ conversion of 93 %, along with NH₃ recovery and purity of 99.14 % and 5.65 % respectively. Hence, the mathematical model demonstrates that an adiabatic packed bed membrane reactor with the integration of heat exchange has the potential to attain greater H₂ conversion compared to the equilibrium constraint observed in a conventional packed bed reactor.

1. Introduction

During the last century, fossil fuels have been the main driver of human development, influencing almost any aspect of the modern society. However, the large utilization of carbon-based fuels led to a dramatic increase in greenhouse gas emissions, carbon dioxide (CO₂) and methane (CH₄), responsible for global warming, air pollution and related issues [1]. In 2022, greenhouse gas emissions increased by 1 %, hitting a new record of 41.3 Gt CO₂-eq [2]. Consequently, to meet the increasing energy needs of the world population, while reducing the anthropogenic impact on the environmental, a new approach and new

energy sources are required to reduce carbon emissions in accordance with international agreements and to drive the current economy to more sustainable choices. In this scenario, the possible utilization of hydrogen (H₂) produced from renewable sources as a cleaner fuel, represents one of the most promising and sustainable options. The hydrogen production via water electrolysis can be powered directly employing electricity obtained from wind or photovoltaic systems [3,4]. Furthermore, gravimetric density of hydrogen is approximately seven times higher than the density of fossil fuels and can be considered a clean energy source, as the only product from its combustion is water [5,6]. Still, the use of hydrogen as an energy carrier is strongly hindered by the problems

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connected with the transport and storage of this gas, due to its highly flammable nature and its high ignition energy even at atmospheric temperatures and pressures [7].

A possible solution to the problem is the storage of hydrogen in chemical carriers, such as ammonia. This chemical-based storage solution is very promising, as all the infrastructure required for the storage and transportation of this bulk chemical are already present and in use. Despite the harsh operative conditions (50–200 bar and 380–500 °C), the vast majority of ammonia is still globally produced via the Haber-Bosch process, that accounts for approximately 2 % of the entire global energy consumption and 1.2 % of global carbon dioxide emissions [8,9]. These energy-intensive conditions are required by the severe thermodynamic and kinetic limitations connected with the ammonia synthesis reaction from nitrogen (N₂) and hydrogen (H₂). As a result, the production of ammonia per single pass remains relatively low, with the effluent ammonia fraction typically in the range of 20–25 % [10,11]. Thus, industrially, conventional ammonia synthesis is conducted in multistage adiabatic packed bed reactors with interstage cooling over an iron-based catalyst [12]. Since ammonia is the sole product of the reaction, a potential strategy to substantially enhance the rate of ammonia synthesis is to shift the equilibrium by continuously removing NH₃ from the reaction zone. This would allow circumventing the thermodynamic equilibrium constrains of conventional reactor and thus be able to operate the ammonia production at lower pressure, with clear advantages in terms of efficiency of the system. However, there have been only relatively few studies in literature that have successfully exceeded single-pass equilibrium conversion for ammonia synthesis. For instance, Smith et al. proposed an integrated ammonia synthesis and separation employing a ruthenium-based catalysts and manganese-based absorbent. The authors demonstrated the advantages of the proposed synergistic system, achieving conversions beyond reaction equilibrium of the conventional system [13]. Wakimoto et al. investigated a recycle (MR) process where a catalytic reactor relates to a membrane separator in series and the retentate stream is recycled to the reactor. NH₃ mole fraction was exceeding the equilibrium mole fraction of 0.01 at 350 °C to 0.1–0.45 in permeate stream [14]. Similar approach was followed by Laciak et al. who proposed the use of molten salt facilitated transport membranes for the selective separation of NH₃ in the recycle stream of the process by standing at T = 250–300 °C [15]. Another study focused on a conceptually different approach of membrane reactor, that utilizes the bipolar diffusion of electrons (e⁻) and nitrogen ions (N₃⁻) in a nitrogen permeation membrane reactor. In this case, Ye et al. shows that at ambient pressure and T = 450 °C, they were able to achieve an ammonia mole fraction close to the limit of the thermodynamic equilibrium [16].

The use of membrane integrated in the reactor is considered as a promising solution to shift the equilibrium of thermodynamically limited catalytic reactions by the selective removal of a product or by-product. This has been applied in various processes such as DME synthesis [17,18] and water-gas shift reaction [19,20]. While the cited studies highlight the advantages offered by the membrane reactor configuration (i.e. enhanced conversion, lower energy requirements for a desired throughput), there are still only a limited number of studies in the open literature on the potential of this technology for ammonia synthesis.

Among these, Zhang et al. discussed the feasibility and advantages of a membrane system in the framework of an isothermal packed-bed membrane reactor with the conventional iron-based catalysts and considered the impact of membrane properties on the reactor performance. The authors found that minimum values of selectivity are necessary to successfully improve the process. Ideally, an ammonia-to-nitrogen selectivity higher than 10 and an ammonia-to-hydrogen selectivity higher than 4 is required. Nevertheless, it has to be pointed out that the authors in this study did not discuss or report the influence of the heat of reaction. Ammonia synthesis is exothermic, thus the heat released by the reaction might as well influence the system from a kinetic and thermodynamic point of view, as well as the stability and

selectivity of the membrane [21]. More recently, Kucuk et al. modelled a structured microreactor, whose channels were coated with iron-based catalyst, with heat exchange and membrane (ZnCl₂ immobilized molten-salt) separation integrated. The proposed system achieved a 47 % nitrogen conversion, surpassing the corresponding equilibrium conversion of 40 %; thus the reported results support the possibility of overcoming the thermodynamic limits in the Haber-Bosch process [22].

This study presents a theoretical study of a non-isothermal one-dimensional packed bed membrane reactor for ammonia synthesis, designed to identify the minimum membrane specifications in terms of ammonia permeance and perm-selectivity, based on the performance of the system. Furthermore, a follow-up study on optimal process conditions study has been performed, particularly focusing on operating temperature and pressure, sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio and sweep gas-to-feed flow molar ratio. The objective is to demonstrate the feasibility of the application of membrane reactor for the ammonia synthesis process with the potential of using milder operating conditions (and subsequent less energy-intensive purification system), and establish a benchmark for membrane technology development.

2. Methodology

2.1. Reactor geometry

The membrane reactor design proposed in this work is illustrated in Fig. 1, which consists of a shell and tube configuration. The inner tube represents a tubular membrane, while the catalyst particles are located in the shell. This configuration establishes two distinct zones: the retentate side, where the feed is introduced and the reaction occurs along the reactor's length, and the permeate side, where the gases selectively permeates the membrane. On the permeate side, a sweep gas is injected and blended with the permeating gas. As illustrated in the figure, the feed flow and the sweep gas flow are in a co-current configuration.

2.2. Reaction scheme and kinetic

Ammonia synthesis involves the reaction between nitrogen and hydrogen, as represented by the following equation (Eq. (1)):

The kinetic model of the reaction was obtained from a previous study by Rossetti et al. that utilized a Ru/C catalyst [23]. The overall structure of the reaction rate is derived from the classical Temkin equation, incorporating an additional adsorption term, as expressed in Eq. (2):

Fig. 1. Packed bed membrane reactor sketch.

$$\frac{d\eta}{d\tau} = k_f \lambda(q) \frac{(a_{N_2})^{0.5} \left[\frac{(a_{H_2})^{0.375}}{(a_{NH_3})^{0.25}} \right] - \frac{1}{K_a} \left[\frac{(a_{NH_3})^{0.75}}{(a_{H_2})^{1.125}} \right]}{1 + K_{H_2} (a_{H_2})^{0.3} + K_{NH_3} (a_{NH_3})^{0.2}} \quad (2)$$

where $\frac{d\eta}{d\tau}$ expresses the reaction rate of the defective reactant in $mol \cdot h^{-1} \cdot L_{cat}^{-1}$, a_i are the partial activities of the involved species, K_a is the reaction equilibrium constant, K_{H_2} and K_{NH_3} are the adsorption equilibrium constant of hydrogen and ammonia respectively, q is the H_2/N_2 molar feed ratio. Therefore $\lambda(q)$ was set to 1 when $H_2/N_2 = 3$ and to 3 when $H_2/N_2 = 1.5$. The aforementioned parameters are determined according to the equations shown in Table 1, where $\beta(q) = 1$ if $q = 3$, $\beta(q) = 0.5$ if $q = 1.5$. η is the fractional conversion depending on x , which is the outlet mole fraction of NH_3 , while the parameter a is set to 2 if $q = 3$ and 2.5 if $q = 1.5$.

2.3. Reactor model

The developed model is a 1-D phenomenological membrane reactor model, grounded on the following assumptions.

- (1) Plug flow behavior, with negligible radial gradients of concentrations and temperature, assuring $\frac{D/2}{L} \ll Re \cdot Sc \ll \frac{L}{D/2}$
- (2) Steady-state conditions
- (3) Negligible pressure drops in the permeate side
- (4) The membrane material is considered inert
- (5) Pseudo-homogeneous model
- (6) Negligible mass- and energy-transport limitations inside the catalyst pellets and at the surface of the pellets
- (7) No catalytic activity is assumed on the permeate side

As expected, these assumptions inherently introduce certain limitations. For example, the pseudo-homogeneous model assumes constant catalyst properties and neglects any radial gradients. To minimize the impact of these simplifications, as noted in Section 3.3, the study was

Table 1

Equations utilized to determine parameters in the kinetic expression of Rossetti et al.

Parameter	Units	Equation
k_f	$mol \cdot h^{-1} \cdot L_{cat}^{-1}$	$9.02 \cdot 10^8 \exp\left(\frac{-23.0}{RT}\right)$
K_a	-	$\exp\left(-2.691122 \log_{10} T - 5.519265 \cdot 10^{-5} T + 1.848863 \cdot 10^{-7} T^2 + \frac{2001.6}{T} + 2.6899\right)$
a_{N_2}	atm	$\frac{1 - \eta \beta(q)}{1 + q - 2 \eta \beta(q)} P \gamma_{N_2}$
a_{H_2}	atm	$\frac{q - 3 \eta \beta(q)}{1 + q - 2 \eta \beta(q)} P \gamma_{H_2}$
a_{NH_3}	atm	$\frac{2 \eta \beta(q)}{1 + q - 2 \eta \beta(q)} P \gamma_{NH_3}$
η	-	$a \left(\frac{x}{1+x} \right)$
γ_{N_2}		$0.93431737 + 0.3101804 \cdot 10^{-3} T + 0.295896 \cdot 10^{-3} P - 0.2707279 \cdot 10^{-6} T^2 + 0.4775207 \cdot 10^{-6} P^2$
γ_{H_2}		$\exp\left[\exp(-3.8402T^{0.125} + 0.541)P - \exp(-0.12637T^{0.5} - 15.98)P^2 + 300 \exp(-0.011901T - 5.941)\left(\exp\left(-\frac{P}{300}\right) - 1\right)\right]$
γ_{NH_3}		$0.1438996 + 0.2028538 \cdot 10^{-2} T - 0.4487672 \cdot 10^{-3} P - 0.1142945 \cdot 10^{-7} T^2 + 0.2761216 \cdot 10^{-6} P^2$
K_{H_2}	$kcal \cdot mol^{-1}$	$\exp\left(\frac{-56.9024}{R} + \frac{37656}{RT}\right)$
K_{NH_3}	$kcal \cdot mol^{-1}$	$\exp\left(\frac{-34.7272}{R} + \frac{29228}{RT}\right)$

conducted using a small-scale reactor. Moreover, assuming steady-state conditions neglect the possibility of accounting for possible fluctuations in concentrations, temperature and pressure. In membrane-assisted systems, such variations would also lead to fluctuations in partial pressure and concentration gradients, thereby reducing permeate flux and overall separation efficiency.

2.3.1. Mass balance equation

The mass balance equations for both retentate and permeate side are presented in this section. The subsequent equations apply to each component of the gas mixture:

$$\frac{dF_i^R}{dL} = \vartheta_i (r_i) \rho_c (1 - \varepsilon) \frac{\pi}{4} (D_r^2 - D_m^2) - J_i (\pi D_m^o) \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{dF_i^P}{dL} = J_i (\pi D_m^o) \quad (4)$$

$$J_i = \mathcal{P}_i (P_i^R - P_i^P) \quad (5)$$

where J_i and \mathcal{P}_i represent the flux and the permeance respectively of the component i permeating through the membrane. The flux is calculated according to Eq. (5) with the pressure difference considered positive when the flow proceeds from the retentate to the permeate side (as such, the results of this study are representative of all pressure driven membrane separations potentially applicable for ammonia recovery in the reactor). It is important to note that the form of this equation depends on the type of membrane being considered. For better clarity, the specific type of membrane used in our study is detailed in Section 3.2.

2.3.2. Energy balance equation

Likewise, the energy balance equations are computed for retentate and permeate side.

$$\sum_i F_i^R C_{P_i}^R \frac{dT^R}{dL} = (r) (-\Delta H)_{T^R} \rho_c (1 - \varepsilon) \frac{\pi}{4} (D_r^2 - D_m^2) - U \pi D_m^i (T^R - T^P) \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_i F_i^P C_{P_i}^P \frac{dT^P}{dL} = U \pi D_m^i (T^R - T^P) \quad (7)$$

Where U is the global heat transfer coefficient, characterizing three successive heat transfer phenomena: 1) the convection in the inner tube, 2) the conduction throughout the membrane and 3) the convection in the outer tube.

$$U = \left(\frac{1}{h^p} + \frac{2 \ln\left(\frac{D_m^o}{D_m^i}\right)}{k} + \frac{D_m^i}{D_m^o} \frac{1}{h^R} \right)^{-1} \quad (8)$$

The heat transfer coefficient in the reaction zone (h^R) was calculated according to the correlation of Li and Finlayson [24], as reported in Eq. (13) which takes in account the heat transfer of a packed bed by referring to a Reynolds number depending on particle diameter, as shown in Eq. (9). As for permeate zone, the heat transfer coefficient (h^P) was calculated according to the correlation of Dittus-Boelter, described in Eq. (14), which consider a smooth concentric annulus [25].

Eq. (9) to Eq. (14) describe the dimensionless numbers employed in this work, which play a crucial role in characterizing the heat and mass transfer phenomena within the system.

$$Re^R = \frac{d_p G^R}{\mu_{mix}^R} \quad (9)$$

$$Re^P = \frac{D_m^i G^P}{\mu_{mix}^P} \quad (10)$$

$$Pr^R = \frac{\mu_{mix}^R c_{p,mix}^R}{\lambda_{mix}^R} \quad (11)$$

$$Pr^P = \frac{\mu_{mix}^P c_{p,mix}^P}{\lambda_{mix}^P} \quad (12)$$

$$Nu^R = 0.17 Re^{0.79} \left(\frac{Pr^P}{0.7} \right)^{1/3} = \frac{h^R d_p}{\lambda_{mix}^R} \quad (13)$$

$$Nu^P = 0.023 Re^{p0.8} Pr^{p0.4} = \frac{h^P d_m}{\lambda_{mix}^P} \quad (14)$$

All the gas properties in terms of density, viscosity, specific heat, thermal conductivity can be found in the supplementary material (SM). In Eq. (15) and Eq. (16), the mass flow rate of the mixture in the retentate and permeate side are provided.

$$G^R = \frac{F_{tot}^R M_{mix}^R}{A} \quad (15)$$

$$G^P = \frac{F_{tot}^P M_{mix}^P}{A_m^i} \quad (16)$$

Lastly the conductivity, which in our case is referred to a carbon-based membrane, was computed by considering the thermal conductivity contribution of the carbon-based layer laying on top of α -Al₂O₃ tubular support. This calculation is based on the correlation presented in the work of Poto et al. [17]. This equation should be updated in case of different types of membranes.

2.3.3. Momentum balance equation

The Ergun equation (Eq. (17)) for the estimation of the pressure drops was implemented only in the retentate side, while keeping constant the pressure on the permeate side.

$$\frac{dP^R}{dL} = - \left(\frac{150 \mu_{mix} u (1 - \varepsilon)^2}{\varepsilon^3 d_p^2} + \frac{1.75 (1 - \varepsilon) \rho_{mix} u^2}{\varepsilon^3 d_p} \right) 10^{-5} \quad (17)$$

Where μ_{mix} and ρ_{mix} are the viscosity and the density of the gas mixture respectively, u is the space velocity based on the empty cross-section of the reactor, ε is the porosity of the bed and d_p is the diameter of the catalyst particles.

2.3.4. Boundary conditions

The boundary conditions applied to solve the model are discussed in this section. At the entrance of the reactor, the inlet temperatures and pressures and the inlet gas compositions, along with the sweep gas are known. Therefore, the following boundary conditions apply at $L = 0$:

$$T^R = T^R(0)$$

$$T^P = T^P(0)$$

$$F_i^R = F_i^R(0), i = 1, 2, 3$$

$$F_i^P = F_i^P(0) \quad i = 1, 2, 3$$

$$P^R = P^R(0)$$

3. Simulation results

The mathematical model consisting of nine ordinary differential equations with corresponding boundary conditions was implemented and solved using *MATLAB R2022a*. The *ode15s* method was employed,

along with a set of algebraic equations concerning reaction rates and gas properties.

The performance of the packed bed membrane reactor is assessed based on H₂ conversion, as expressed in Eq. (18). The different definition of conversion relates to the porous nature of the membrane. In fact, the separation process in this context relies on the physical size of the membrane pores relative to the molecules being separated.

$$x_{H_2} = \frac{F_{H_2,in}^R - F_{H_2,out}^R - F_{H_2,tm}^R}{F_{H_2,in}^R - F_{H_2,tm}^*} \quad (18)$$

Where:

$$F_{H_2,tm} = F_{H_2,out}^P - F_{H_2,in}^P$$

$$F_{H_2,tm}^* = F_{H_2,out}^P - F_{H_2,in}^P \quad \text{only if } F_{H_2,tm}^* = < 0$$

Due to the non-ideal membrane performance, in our case, not only ammonia is separated, but some hydrogen/nitrogen also permeates through the membrane. This represents a loss of reagent in the retentate, which must be taken in account in the conversion definition. As shown in Fig. 2, *trans*-membrane flow, previously defined as $F_{H_2,tm}$ for hydrogen, is considered positive when hydrogen exits the reaction zone. Consequently, it must be subtracted from the total available hydrogen in this zone. However, if the hydrogen partial pressure on the permeate side exceeds that on the retentate side, a back-permeation phenomenon may occur. In this scenario, hydrogen permeates back into the retentate side, as illustrated in Fig. 2, effectively increasing the amount of reagent present in this zone. This additional hydrogen has to be accounted for in the total reacting hydrogen. In the model, when back-permeation occurs, the net flux of hydrogen entering the retentate becomes negative according to the definition. In the following study it is going to be expressed as $F_{H_2,bp}$. Additionally, other parameters, such as *NH₃ recovery* and *NH₃ purity*, as outlined in Eqs. (19) and (20) respectively, were evaluated to assess the performances of the PBMR. *NH₃ recovery* indicates the proportion of ammonia that can be collected on the permeate side, compared to its production in the retentate. Meanwhile *NH₃ purity* provides insight into the composition of the stream exiting the membrane, offering essential data to the subsequent separation step.

$$NH_3 \text{ recovery} = \frac{F_{NH_3}^P}{F_{NH_3}^R + F_{NH_3}^P} \quad (19)$$

$$NH_3 \text{ purity} = \frac{F_{NH_3}^P}{F_{N_2}^P + F_{H_2}^P + F_{NH_3}^P} \quad (20)$$

3.1. Validation of the packed bed reactor

Before delving into the reactor's performance, the mathematical model was first validated by comparing its predictions with experimental data retrieved from Rossetti et al. [23]. The validation included

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of gas flow through porous membrane.

the data set of 16 kinetic tests performed within a temperature range of 370–460 °C and a pressure range of 50–100 bar, with two different H₂/N₂ feed ratio, i.e. 1.5 and 3, and varying gas hourly space velocity (GHSV), in the range of $(0.5\text{--}4) \cdot 10^5 \text{ h}^{-1}$, defined as the ratio of the normal feed flow rate and the catalyst volume. In order to ensure the validity of the mathematical model, a sensitivity study was carried out, by varying the bed porosity (ϵ) and consequently the active bed length (which is not reported by Rossetti et al.). As illustrated in Fig. 3, bed porosity values between 0.3 and 0.5 were investigated. From this study however it was found that variation in bed porosity had a negligible impact on the final result. This can be explained by the fact that the reaction is fast and can rapidly reach the quasi-steady state, allowing the reactants to equilibrate rapidly. Details of the validation study for all the other tests are provided in the SM. To assess the model's accuracy, Mean Absolute Error (MAE) was employed as the principal validation metric, calculated as follow:

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_{NH_3}^{exp} - y_{NH_3}^{model}|$$

Where n represents the number of data points in each test set. Additionally, a parity plot was employed to visualize all the data in a single representation (Fig. 4)

3.2. Validation of the permeation module

Once the packed bed reactor was validated, the model was extended to incorporate a membrane, by using Eqs. (3) and (4). In this extended model, the permeation process accounted only for pressure changes and did not include temperature dependency.

In this overview, the choice of an ammonia permeable membrane for a membrane reactor is critical, and various types of membranes can be considered. The selection of a membrane is influenced by various factors, including operating conditions (such as temperature, pressure), feedstock composition, and the required product purity. Additionally, the chemical resistance and long-term stability are of crucial considerations. Membrane materials used in ammonia synthesis and separation include molten salts based membrane [15], polymeric membranes [26], ceramic membranes such as zeolite membranes [27,28] and silica membranes [29].

This validation step focuses on ceramic porous membranes, particularly carbon membranes [30], due to their chemical resistance, cost-effectiveness and the tunable properties. Although no studies in literature have explored their use with ammonia, the same research group is currently working on developing new formulations specifically for this application. From this phase of research, experimental gas permeation tests were carried out in the laboratory to evaluate the membrane's performance under relevant conditions (i.e. high

Fig. 4. Parity plot showing the distribution of experiments vs. model prediction.

temperature and different pressure). For the availability of data obtained from these tests, it was decided to integrate them into the mathematical model to validate its accuracy and predictive capability. Specifically, considering that no reaction was occurring, the model successfully predicted the permeance of each component at different delta pressure across the membrane (as shown in Fig. 5). This validation process confirmed the accuracy of the membrane reactor model.

3.3. Study of the membrane performance

Preliminary studies were conducted on the isothermal membrane reactor to examine how the membrane's performance would impact the reactor's capabilities in terms of hydrogen conversion, ammonia recovery and purity. All the operational conditions and design specifications of the reactor selected for this study are detailed in Table 2 where.

- ❖ Temperature and pressure were established based on the lower boundary limit where the kinetic law was determined.
- ❖ Sub-stoichiometric feed ratio was selected due to the hydrogen poisoning associated with Ru-based catalysts. In this case the conversion is reported in terms of H₂ conversion, being the limiting reagent.
- ❖ Reactor length and diameter were chosen to ensure $L/D > 30$, guaranteeing negligible radial dispersion [31].

Fig. 3. Model prediction of ammonia outlet molar fraction from experimental tests at $T = 430 \text{ °C}$ and $P = 100 \text{ bar}$ for $GHSV = (0.5\text{--}4) \cdot 10^5 \text{ h}^{-1}$ for (a) H₂/N₂ = 1.5 (b) H₂/N₂ = 3.

Fig. 5. Permeation module validation with experimental test at $\Delta P = (1-6)$ bar and $T = 300$ °C for (a) pure N_2 permeance, (b) pure H_2 permeance and (c) pure NH_3 permeance.

Table 2

Packed bed membrane reactor parameters in isothermal conditions.

Parameter	Symbol	Units	Value
Retentate temperature	T^R	°C	370
Retentate pressure	P^R	bar	50
H_2/N_2 feed ratio (ret. & perm.)	q	$\text{mol}_{H_2} \text{mol}_{N_2}^{-1}$	1.5
Sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio	SW	-	1
Pressure difference across the membrane	ΔP	bar	0
Reactor length	L	m	1
Reactor diameter	D	m	0.033
Gas hourly space velocity	$GHSV$	h^{-1}	35
Bed porosity	ϵ	$\text{m}_v^3 \text{m}_r^{-3}$	0.4
Catalyst bed density	ρ_c	kg m_c^{-3}	590

- ❖ SW , which is the sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio, was selected to match the feed in the retentate.
- ❖ The Peclet number was employed to determine the appropriate axial velocity to neglect axial dispersion.

In this case as well, the presence of axial dispersion would indicate a deviation from ideal plug flow, introducing back-mixing along the reactor length and potentially reducing the overall conversion efficiency. In membrane systems, this would further diminish the effective driving force for separation, negatively impacting overall performance.

3.3.1. Ideal membrane case study

In assessing potential membrane performance benchmarks, selectivity (S_{NH_3/H_2} , S_{NH_3/N_2} , S_{H_2/N_2}) as well as permeance of each gas were considered during this study. The literature survey, on hypothetical membranes suitable for NH_3 separation, revealed that ceramic

membranes, specifically silica and zeolite membranes, are suitable for ammonia separation. Therefore their already existing performance were chosen as a reference. For instance, Camus et al. observed $\mathcal{P}_{NH_3} \sim (10^{-8} - 10^{-7}) \text{ mol Pa}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ at 80 °C and 10 bar [28], meanwhile Kanezashi et al. investigated silica membrane over a wide range of temperatures, reporting $\mathcal{P}_{NH_3} \sim (10^{-9}) \text{ mol Pa}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ [29]. Thus, in the first attempt the range investigated for the ammonia permeance was $\mathcal{P}_{NH_3} = [0 - 10^{-6}]$. The membrane was considered to be ideal, implying that the pore size distribution was designed to exclusively allow the passage of ammonia and hydrogen, as they possess the smallest molecules with very similar kinetic diameters (0.26 nm and 0.29 nm respectively). Thus, during the simulations, nitrogen permeation was neglected, resulting in $S_{H_2/N_2} = \infty$ and $S_{NH_3/N_2} = \infty$. Considering the potential transport mechanisms evolving within the membrane, molecular sieving would be the most preferred phenomenon, as it enable separation based on the kinetic diameter of the single molecule. Conversely, if the pores are larger and not tailored to exclusively permit ammonia passage, the transport mechanism could shift towards Knudsen diffusion transport [30]. For this mechanism the Knudsen selectivity results to be $S_{NH_3/H_2} = \sqrt{M_{H_2}/M_{NH_3}} = 0.34$. This value was taken as reference to set the selectivity range to study, which turned to be $S_{NH_3/H_2} = [0.5 - 50]$.

Hydrogen conversion is significantly influenced by the ammonia permeance of the membrane, as shown in Fig. 6 (a). The increasing trend reaches a plateau when $\mathcal{P}_{NH_3} = 0.4 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ mol Pa}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, indicating that the system has achieved thermodynamic equilibrium between the reaction and permeation zone. However, in all the cases, the achieved conversion exceeded that of the packed bed reactor, corresponding to 31.4 %. The investigation on hydrogen conversion as a function of NH_3 permeance, evaluated at different S_{NH_3/H_2} values, demonstrates that for

Fig. 6. Study of membrane performance impact with respect to NH_3 permeance and parametric to S_{NH_3/H_2} on (a) H_2 conversion, (b) NH_3 transmembrane flow, (c) H_2 back-permeation flow and (d) NH_3 recovery.

value greater than $0.4 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ mol Pa}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ no further improvement is observed. These results align with previous literature studies [21].

In Fig. 6 (b) the ammonia transmembrane molar flow ($F_{NH_3,tm}$) is expressed as a function of NH_3 permeance for different value of S_{NH_3/H_2} . The results show that the ammonia molar flow does not increase significantly with the selectivity, indicating that this molar flow depends primarily on NH_3 permeance rather than the selectivity of the membrane. Although an increase in permeance is observed, it is not substantial enough to significantly impact the passage of ammonia across the membrane and, consequently, the hydrogen conversion.

Afterward, the study focused on hydrogen back-permeating from the permeate to the retentate, i.e. $F_{H_2,bp}$. Fig. 6. (c) shows that this molar flow increases along with the NH_3 permeance increase (negative sign indicates opposite direction respect to the mass balance equation), whereas the flow decreases when the selectivity increases. This behavior can be explained by the fact that an increase in S_{NH_3/H_2} , results in less hydrogen loss from the retentate side, maintaining a higher partial pressure and reducing the driving force from the permeate to the retentate side, thus leading to a decrease in back-permeation.

Avoiding excessive hydrogen accumulation in the retentate zone is crucial due to catalyst-related reasons, and a loss of hydrogen in the permeate zone necessitates additional sweep gas reintegration. Moreover, with less H_2 back permeation, NH_3 partial pressure in the permeate is kept low, allowing enhanced ammonia permeation. Thus, as shown in Fig. 6(d), an higher ammonia-to-hydrogen selectivity enables a higher NH_3 recovery, reaching a maximum at $S_{NH_3} = 0.1 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ mol Pa}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. This latter value was selected as final value together with selectivity $S_{NH_3/H_2} = 50$ and considered for the rest of the study.

3.3.2. Real membrane case study

After this initial optimization, also nitrogen permeation was considered, hence also the influence of S_{NH_3/N_2} was examined. A broad range of selectivity values was selected based on literature studies. As shown in Fig. 7 (a) there is no significant correlation between conversion and selectivity, even with a three-order magnitude increase. This observation is consistent with the findings reported by Zhang et al. [21].

Therefore, the amount of loss nitrogen in the retentate side, $F_{N_2,tm}$, was evaluated as key performance parameter to identify the minimum required ammonia-to-nitrogen selectivity. The results reported in Fig. 7 (b) indicate that with low selectivity values, the nitrogen flow decreases, and beyond a selectivity value of approximately 100, the decrease becomes less pronounced. Analyzing the trends in ammonia recovery and purity, shown in Fig. 7 (c), they exhibit an opposite behavior. This phenomenon is linked to the fact that as S_{NH_3/N_2} increases, less nitrogen reaches the permeate side. This leads to have lowers partial pressure of ammonia in the retentate, making it more difficult to effectively separate the produced ammonia. At the same time, more ammonia is being generated due to a higher nitrogen concentration in the feed, creating a complex trade-off. This circumstance results in a higher ammonia concentration in the retentate zone, with some ammonia not being fully removed by the membrane, leading to a decrease in its recovery. In contrast, purity follows the opposite trend, increasing as expected, since more ammonia is separated while less nitrogen crossing the membrane. Based on these findings, a minimum value of $S_{NH_3/N_2} = 100$ is set as required parameter for the membrane.

In Fig. 8, H_2 conversion is depicted as a function of both ammonia-to-nitrogen and ammonia-to hydrogen selectivity under three different NH_3 permeance scenarios. The result indicates that as ammonia

Fig. 7. Study of membrane performance impact with respect to S_{NH_3/N_2} on (a) H_2 conversion, (b) N_2 transmembrane flow, (c) NH_3 purity and NH_3 recovery.

permeance increases, a corresponding rise in H_2 conversion is observed. For each S_{NH_3/H_2} value, the conversion consistently reaches a plateau at $S_{NH_3/N_2} = 100$. Similar trends are observed in NH_3 purity and recovery, as illustrated in Fig. S. 2 and Fig. S. 3 respectively. Focusing on the N_2 conversion (Fig. S. 6), a decreasing trend is observed with increase of S_{NH_3/H_2} . This behavior might be due to the S_{H_2/N_2} decrease when the S_{NH_3/H_2} increases, resulting in a greater possibility of N_2 permeating the membrane. N_2 transmembrane is increasing with selectivity, leaving less N_2 available to react in the retentate side. On the other side, H_2 conversion increases with selectivity due to the dependence from the back-permeation which decreases as the selectivity increases. Similar considerations apply to the stream purity which decreases with S_{NH_3/H_2} increment. This condition eventually reaches a plateau when $\mathcal{S}_{NH_3} = 10^{-7} mol Pa^{-1} m^{-2} s^{-1}$. At this point, while the N_2 transmembrane flow still depends on selectivity, the amount of NH_3 passing through the membrane becomes less dependent on selectivity and stabilizes at this permeance value, as previously mentioned. Nevertheless, higher ammonia recovery can be achieved, as it depends solely on the ammonia molar flow across the membrane, which increases with ammonia permeance and, simultaneously, with NH_3 selectivity over N_2 and H_2 . As a result $\mathcal{S}_{NH_3} = 10^{-7} mol Pa^{-1} m^{-2} s^{-1}$ demonstrates optimal performance is achieved when coupled with a S_{NH_3/H_2} of approximately 50 and a S_{NH_3/N_2} of approximately 100, found as a trade-off between conversion, purity and recovery results.

Optimal membrane features determined at the end of this study are detailed in Table 3. In the context of possible membranes suitable for this process, described in section 3.3.1, namely silica-based and zeolite-based membranes it is important to identify the limitations associated with them. Silica membranes, despite their good ammonia selectivity, are prone to cracking or failure under mechanical stress or thermal cycling. Additionally, producing defect-free silica membranes is often

expensive. Zeolite membranes, on the other hand, may suffer from ammonia adsorption during prolonged operation, potentially blocking active pores and reducing separation efficiency. Their synthesis is also costly, requiring high-purity precursors and precise fabrication conditions.

3.4. Operational condition study: SW vs transmembrane pressure difference

It is crucial to maintain a high partial pressure difference of ammonia across the membrane to enhance the driving force and, consequently, ammonia separation. To achieve this, a strategic approach involves utilizing gases in the permeate to minimize the partial pressure of ammonia on that side. Simultaneously, the partial pressure of the reactants must be high enough to prevent their passage across the membrane. To address this challenge, a sweep gas composed of the two reactants, H_2 and N_2 , was considered. The investigation initially focused on an adiabatic solution without considering heat exchange in shell and tube reactor configuration. Afterward heat exchange is considered between retentate gases and sweep gas. In this context, Eqs. (6) and (7) were applied within the model, accounting for all the gas properties depending on temperature, as detailed in the supplementary materials (SM). Finally, a parametric study of sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio (hereafter indicated by SW) and transmembrane pressure difference (hereafter indicated by ΔP) was conducted to assess the potential impact on reactor performance. As mentioned before, the inlet reaction temperature was established based on lower limit of the kinetic rate law. Thus, for simplicity the conditions of the reactor were kept the same as before, and the sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio inlet temperature was also set at $370^\circ C$. Pressure in the permeate was varied according to the desired ΔP in the case study, ranging up to a maximum of 50 bar which aligns with the pressure on the retentate side. The outcomes of this

Fig. 8. Study of membrane performance impact on H_2 conversion relative to S_{NH_3/N_2} and parametric to S_{NH_3/H_2} with (a) $\mathcal{P}_{NH_3} = 10^{-9} \text{ mol Pa}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, (b) $\mathcal{P}_{NH_3} = 10^{-8} \text{ mol Pa}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and (c) $\mathcal{P}_{NH_3} = 10^{-7} \text{ mol Pa}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

Table 3

Optimal membrane features determined at the end of this study.

Membrane optimal conditions	Units	Value
\mathcal{P}_{NH_3}	$\text{mol Pa}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$	10^{-7}
S_{NH_3/H_2}	-	50
S_{NH_3/N_2}	-	100

parametric study (yet without heat exchange) are presented in Fig. 9 (a) where the conversion is assessed across a range of SW value between 0 and 50 for each ΔP . As SW increases, the conversion rises, and eventually reaches a plateau. However, the rate at which this plateau is attained is determined by the pressure. This phenomenon occurs because the increase in SW leads to a decrease in the partial pressure of ammonia in the sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio stream, thereby enhancing the driving force for ammonia permeation through the membrane. At the same time, a larger pressure difference between retentate and permeate creates a stronger driving force, facilitating the migration of the species from retentate to permeate. As a matter of fact, as ΔP increases, the plateau is achieved more rapidly, together with a higher conversion. Consequently, it can be inferred that once the sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio rate attains a sufficiently high value, further increases do not significantly lower the partial pressure of ammonia in the sweep gas, leading to a negligible change in terms of hydrogen conversion.

Likewise, when considering the heat exchange between retentate and permeate zone, shown in Fig. 9 (b), for each ΔP value, the plateau of the conversion is reached at a lower SW, accompanied by a simultaneous inversion of the trend. This effect arises because, as SW increases, the residence time in the permeate decreases, resulting in faster NH_3 removal. Simultaneously, an increase in ΔP , promotes additional NH_3 separation which accelerates the reaction rate, alongside a rise in temperature. However, the velocity eventually reaches a speed at which

further increases in SW yields no additional improvement. At this breakthrough point, as ΔP continues to rise, the reaction accelerates but the conversion rate subsequently starts to decline due to elevated temperature. Thus for $SW \leq 6$, higher ΔP leads to higher conversion, whereas as SW increases, the conversion trend rises with a decrease in ΔP . Additionally, larger ΔP values result in a quicker attainment of the plateau, and in all the cases, the achieved conversion is consistently higher than in the no-heat exchange case. As a matter of fact considering the heat exchange between the two concentric tubes, the temperature profile is kept much more uniform (Fig. 10 (a)) than the other cases, leading to reach higher conversion, due to the presence of the sweep gas, acting as cooling fluid, in view of the exothermicity of the reaction. In this case, as ΔP decreases, a reduced driving force is established between the two parts, causing less loss of sweep gas towards the retentate side. This helps in maintaining a high amount of cooling gas in the permeate side. In contrast, when examining the parameters of ammonia recovery and purity (Fig. 9c and d), it becomes evident that their upward trends are contingent on the increase in ΔP . This aligns with expectations since a higher pressure difference results in a higher different partial pressure of ammonia, allowing more ammonia to pass through and be separated. As the sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio increases, more hydrogen and nitrogen are present in the permeate, leading to a decrease in purity. In terms of recovery factor, when the driving force decreases, obviously less ammonia can be detached, leading to a lower ammonia recovery. Thus, a $\Delta P = 40$ bar and $SW = 6$ have been picked as best trade-off conditions from this analysis, for the membrane reactor.

3.5. Heat management study: effect of temperature

The mathematical model with the implementation of all the discussed parameters was further analyzed with a focus on heat management, considering the sweep gas as a cooling fluid. Fig. 10 (a) highlights

Fig. 9. Effect of the sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio (SW), parametric with ΔP , considering adiabatic conditions, on (a) H_2 conversion without heat exchange, (b) H_2 conversion considering heat exchange between retentate and permeate, (c) NH_3 purity and (d) NH_3 recovery considering heat exchange between retentate and permeate.

two different cases: the dash-dotted lines illustrate the temperature profile of an adiabatic membrane reactor without considering heat exchange between retentate and sweep gases, whereas the solid ones depict the temperature profile of an adiabatic membrane reactor when heat transfer between these zones is considered. This demonstrates that the presence of a sweep gas contributes to a more stable temperature profile, promoting higher conversion. Furthermore Fig. 10 (b) shows the temperature profile of both sides for the specific case of $SW = 10$, where it is shown that the sweep gas temperature profile slowly increases. As the retentate releases heat to the permeate, temperature peaks in the retentate are moderated, resulting in a flatter temperature gradient.

Interestingly, using the optimized conditions in paragraph 3.4, adjusting the sweep gas-to-feed inlet temperature on the permeate side, the final conversion can be enhanced even further. Fig. 11 (a) illustrates this investigation by varying the inlet permeate temperature, revealing that at $T_{in}^p = 200$ °C the highest conversion is achieved. This outcome is due to the fact that, as soon as the temperatures decrease, the sweep gas acts as a cooling fluid, lowering the reaction temperature and consequently improving achievable conversions. Additionally, as T_{in}^p increases, the heat driving force between the two zones decreases. Fig. 11 (b) shows the final temperature reached both in retentate and permeate side by varying the inlet sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio temperature. This clearly shows that the permeate stream is not able to completely cool down the retentate stream. Therefore, an extra cooling strategy would be needed.

3.6. On the effect of sweep gas-to-feed molar feed ratio

A key factor affecting ammonia production is the H_2/N_2 feed flow ratio. In this specific study a value of 1.5 was selected to leverage the favorable activity of the ruthenium-based catalyst in an under-stoichiometric environment. As a consequence, the sweep gas-to-feed molar feed ratio was consistently kept constant to the retentate side one. The composition of the sweep gas-to-feed is crucial because it directly impacts both the efficiency of ammonia removal and the reaction equilibrium.

Fig. 12 presents two scenarios using different feed molar ratios in the permeate side and sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio to highlight how these factors affect reactor performance in terms of hydrogen conversion and ammonia purity, with respect to the ΔP . In Fig. 13 (a) when using $SW = 0$, the feed ratio shows no effect, as expected, whereas ΔP plays a more crucial role. As ΔP increases, hydrogen conversion rises, due to the large ammonia partial pressure difference across the membrane. Simultaneously, also an increase in ammonia purity is observed due to the lack of gas in the permeate stream. Fig. 13 (b), shows the case study for $SW = 6$, where the maximum H_2 conversion is reached at $\Delta P = 20$ bar. For ΔP below this value, the conversion is slightly lower when $H_2/N_2 = 3$. The reason is correlated to a different partial pressure for the reactants (i.e. higher hydrogen concentration in the permeate), leading to a potential back-permeation effect. However, this difference diminishes as the pressure in the permeate decreases, reaching a maximum before experiencing a slight decline with further increases in ΔP (see section 3.4). Fig. 13, representing 1.5 and 3 sweep gas-to-feed flow molar ratios respectively, illustrate the reactor's performance with a SW ranging from 0 to 10. It is evident that in both cases, the highest conversion is achieved with $SW = 6-10$ at $\Delta P = 20$, with the behavior reversing as the difference of pressure increases. As anticipated $SW = 0$ allows for the highest purity, but it results in the lowest conversion. For the optimal reactor parameters, setting $SW = 6$ or $SW = 10$ at high ΔP does not yield a significant difference in terms of conversion. However, $SW = 6$ appears to offer an advantage in terms of ammonia purity. Therefore $SW = 6$ was selected as the final value, regardless of the molar feed ratio of the sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio, along with a $\Delta P = 20$ bar. For a precise determination of the optimal reactor parameters, an economic evaluation would be necessary to identify the most cost-effective choice.

Fig. 10. Temperature profile along the reactor length considering an (a) adiabatic packed bed membrane reactor including heat exchange (HE) and not, between retentate and permeate side, (b) temperature profile in the retentate and permeate side for the scenario of SW = 10 and $\Delta P = 40$ bar.

Fig. 11. Study of the effect of the permeate flow inlet temperature (T_{in}^P) on (a) H_2 conversion and (b) outlet temperature of permeate (T_{out}^P) and retentate (T_{out}^R).

Fig. 12. Effect of ΔP on H_2 conversion and NH_3 purity for (a) SW = 0 and (b) SW = 6, with a parametric study of sweep gas-to-feed molar ratio $H_2/N_2 = 1.5$ and 3.

3.7. Membrane reactor vs. packed bed reactor

With the implementation of the membrane performance, it was possible to study and compare two different reactor configurations: a conventional packed bed reactor and a packed bed membrane reactor. The optimal operating conditions of the membrane reactor are summarized in Table 4.

Fig. 14 (a) presents in the first instance the isothermal case scenario where the conversion trend along the reactor length clearly

demonstrates the benefits of membrane integration. This configuration effectively overcome the severe limitations imposed by thermodynamic equilibrium, here set at $T = 370$ °C and $P = 50$ bar under isothermal conditions. Because of the selective removal of ammonia via the membrane, the equilibrium constraint on hydrogen conversion can be shifted, resulting in higher overall conversion and improved ammonia recovery yield.

Fig. 14 (b) shows a comparison between a conventional packed bed reactor with a packed bed membrane reactor under adiabatic

Fig. 13. Effect of ΔP on H_2 conversion and NH_3 purity for different molar feed ratio of sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio (a) $H_2/N_2 = 1.5$ and (b) $H_2/N_2 = 3$, with a parametric study of $SW = 0, 6$ and 10 .

Fig. 14. Comparison of performance in terms of H_2 conversion for a conventional reactor and a membrane reactor operated under (a) isothermal and (b) adiabatic conditions.

Table 4
Optimal operative conditions of the packed bed membrane reactor.

Parameter	Symbol	Units	Value
Retentate temperature	T^R	$^{\circ}C$	370
Permeate temperature	T^P	$^{\circ}C$	200
Retentate pressure	p^R	bar	50
Pressure difference across the membrane	ΔP	bar	20
H_2/N_2 feed ratio (ret & perm)	q	$mol_{H_2} mol_{N_2}^{-1}$	1.5
Sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio	SW	-	6
NH_3 permeance	\mathcal{S}_{NH_3}	$mol Pa^{-1} m^{-2} s^{-1}$	10^{-7}
NH_3 to H_2 selectivity	S_{NH_3/H_2}	-	50
NH_3 to N_2 selectivity	S_{NH_3/N_2}	-	100
Reactor length	L	m	1
Reactor diameter	D	m	0.033

conditions. In the conventional reactor, where operational conditions and design are chosen to reach equilibrium conversion, conversion remains nearly constant, as the reaction completes within the first few centimeters of the reactor length. The adiabatic membrane reactor achieves a final conversion that exceeds the one of the conventional adiabatic reactor by approximately 63 %, revealing the feasibility of this technology for ammonia synthesis application. The comparison of the membrane reactor performance considering heat exchange between retentate and permeate side is showed in Fig. 15. The red continuous line indicates a temperature peak at the inlet of the reactor, a result of the high reaction rate in this region. Therefore, the co-current choice assure the highest driving force in this zone.

Fig. 15. H_2 conversion and retentate temperature in PBR and PBMR configurations. Comparison between adiabatic and non-adiabatic operations.

4. Conclusions

The current study investigated the impact of a membrane-enhanced process on ammonia production, developing a 1-D phenomenological non-isothermal reactor model, to analyze how the membrane's performance could influence the feasibility of the process. Initially, the model

was validated using experimental tests conducted on a Ru/C catalyst. Subsequently, the membrane was incorporated into the isothermal model, and it was used as demonstration of the impact of membrane application on the process. Under base conditions ($T^R = 370\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $P^R = 50\text{ bar}$, $H_2/N_2 = 1.5$, $SW = 1$, $\Delta P = 0$) the results demonstrated a substantial enhancement in H_2 conversion upon introducing the membrane into the packed bed reactor. Notably, an NH_3 selectivity of 50 towards H_2 and 100 towards N_2 , along with a minimum NH_3 permeance requirement of $10^{-7}\text{ mol Pa}^{-1}\text{ m}^{-2}\text{ s}^{-1}$, exceeded the thermodynamic equilibrium limits of the conventional packed bed reactor.

The study delved into the influence of various process parameters. Simulations were performed for different co-current sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio values, with the application of ΔP across the membrane, showing the possibility to further improve the reactor performance in terms of H_2 conversion. However, after the sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio reached a plateau, further increases in SW flow rate did not lead to any additional conversion change. The optimal conditions were found for $SW = 6$ and $\Delta P = 20\text{ bar}$. Considering the sweep gas as a cooling fluid, the study of heat exchange between the two sides revealed improved performance. Analyzing the temperature gradient highlighted the importance of treating the sweep gas as a cooling fluid, allowing a controlled temperature profile and, thereby, improved reactor performance by adjusting the permeate side temperature. Finally, investigating the sweep gas-to-feed molar feed ratio revealed that a value of $H_2/N_2 = 1.5$ and $SW = 6$ lead to reach the maximum hydrogen conversion of 93 % and simultaneously higher NH_3 purity and recovery, 5.65 % and 99.14 % respectively at the first half of the reactor length.

The results suggest that membrane reactors offer a promising route for improving the efficiency of the ammonia synthesis process, reducing overall energy consumption and operational costs. This can be achieved through lower operating pressures, equilibrium shifting via selective separation, reduced recycling and separation energy, enhanced heat integration, and decreased feedstock and catalyst usage, improving both efficiency and cost-effectiveness.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2025.150995>.

Nomenclature

A	m^2	Internal reactor cross section
A_m^i	m^2	Internal membrane cross section
a_i	atm	Activity coefficient of species i
$c_{p_{mix}}^R, c_{p_{mix}}^P$	$J\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ K}^{-1}$	Heat capacity of the mixture gas in the retentate and permeate side
ΔH_{298K}	$kJ\text{ mol}^{-1}$	Heat of reaction at 298 K
$(-\Delta H)_{T^R}$	$kJ\text{ mol}^{-1}$	Heat of reaction at T^R
ΔP	bar	Pressure difference across the membrane
D	m	Reactor diameter
D_i^r	m	Inner reactor diameter
D_m^O	m	Outer membrane diameter
D_m^i	m	Internal membrane diameter
d_p	m	Particle diameter
$F_{i,lm}$	$mol\text{ h}^{-1}$	Retentate molar flow crossing the membrane to the permeate
$F_{i,bp}$	$mol\text{ h}^{-1}$	Permeate molar flow crossing the membrane to the retentate
F_i^R, F_i^P	$mol\text{ h}^{-1}$	Retentate and permeate molar flow of the species i
F_{tot}^R	$mol\text{ h}^{-1}$	Total retentate molar flow rate
G^R, G^P	$kg\text{ m}^{-2}\text{ s}^{-1}$	Total mass flow rate in retentate and permeate side
$GHSV$	h^{-1}	Gas hourly space velocity based on catalyst volume
h^R, h^P	$W\text{ m}^{-2}\text{ K}^{-1}$	Heat transfer coefficient in the retentate and permeate side
J_i	$mol\text{ m}^{-2}\text{ h}^{-1}$	Permeation flux of the species i
K_a	–	Equilibrium constant of the reaction, in terms of activities
K_{H_2}	$kcal\text{ mol}^{-1}$	Adsorption equilibrium constant of hydrogen
K_{NH_3}	$kcal\text{ mol}^{-1}$	Adsorption equilibrium constant of ammonia
k	$W\text{ m}^{-1}\text{ K}^{-1}$	Thermal conductivity of the carbon membrane
k_f	$mol\text{ h}^{-1}L_{cat}^{-1}$	Kinetic constant of the direct reaction

(continued on next page)

While the current study assumes a 1-D pseudo-homogenous model with ideal plug flow and steady-state conditions for simplicity, future work should focus on extending the model by incorporating axial and radial dispersion, as well as radial diffusion, to account for possible deviations from ideal flow and concentration profiles, especially in larger or industrial scale systems where these effects can be non-negligible. Finally, future work should aim to assess whether the adoption of a more detailed heterogeneous model, accounting for interphase and intra-particle transport limitations, is necessary to accurately capture the system behavior under different conditions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Iolanda Gargiulo: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Gaetano Anello:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Simon Richard:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Fausto Gallucci:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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(continued)

L	m	Reactor length
M_{mix}^R, M_{mix}^P	$g\ mol^{-1}$	Molar mass of gaseous mixture in the retentate and permeate side
Nu^R, Nu^P	–	Nusselt number in the retentate and permeate side
p^R	bar	Pressure in the retentate side
\mathcal{P}_i	$mol\ Pa^{-1} m^{-2} s^{-1}$	Permeance of the species i
P_i^R, P_i^P	bar	Partial pressure of the species i in the retentate and permeate side
PBR		Conventional Packed Bed Reactor
PBMR		Packed Bed Membrane Reactor
Pr^R, Pr^P	–	Prandtl number in the retentate and permeate side
q	$mol_{H_2}, mol_{N_2}^{-1}$	H_2/N_2 molar feed ratio
r	$mol\ h^{-1} L_{cat}^{-1}$	Reaction rate
R	$J\ mol^{-1} K^{-1}$	Ideal gas constant
Re^R, Re^P	–	Reynolds number in the retentate and permeate side
S_{ij}	–	Selectivity of the species i over the species j
Sc	–	Schmidt number
SW	–	Sweep gas-to-feed flow ratio
T^R, T^P	K	Temperature in the retentate and permeate side
U	$W\ m^{-2} K^{-1}$	Global heat transfer coefficient
u	$m\ s^{-1}$	Space velocity based on the empty cross-section of the bed
Greek symbols		
$dn/d\tau$	$mol\ h^{-1} L_{cat}^{-1}$	Rate of consumption of the reactant
$\beta(q)$	–	Constant
γ_i	–	Fugacity coefficient of the species i
ϵ	$m_p^3 m_r^{-3}$	Bed porosity
η	–	Fractional conversion
θ_i	–	Stoichiometric coefficient
$\lambda(q)$	–	Stoichiometric parameter
$\lambda_{mix}^R, \lambda_{mix}^P$	$W\ m^{-1} K^{-1}$	Thermal conductivity of the gas mixture in the retentate and permeate side
μ_{mix}^R, μ_{mix}^P	$Pa\ s$	Viscosity of the gas mixture
ρ_c	$kg_{cat}\ m_{cat}^{-3}$	Catalyst density
ρ_{mix}	$mol\ m^{-3}$	Density of the gas mixture in the retentate
Superscript		
i	Internal/Inner	
o	Outer	
P	Permeate	
R	Retentate	
r	Reactor	
Subscript		
bp	Back-permeation	
c	Catalyst	
i	Species	
in	Inlet	
m	Membrane	
mix	Gas mixture	
out	Outlet	
p	Particle	
tm	Trans-Membrane	

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